

Table for Lay Public Dissemination

Acronym	<p>QUAPROEST</p> <p><i>Illustration 1: Calibration procedure of Solo quadruped</i></p>
Name of user	<p>Médéric Fourmy</p>
Title	<p>Quadruped robot proprioceptive estimation</p>
Objectives (Max 150 words, Calibri 11)	<p>The objectives of the stays are twofold. First, we implement and fine tune an inertial kinematics estimator (proprioceptive) estimator for legged robots. The implementation is undertaken using the WOLF estimation framework which is developed at IRI's Mobile Robotics Laboratory. Secondly, we test the estimator on quadruped robot Solo. Validation of the algorithm is done using the Mobile Robotics Laboratory motion capture system (Optitrack).</p>
Impact (Max 150 words, Calibri 11)	<p>Important progress was made on the estimator implementation. Many calibration experiments were done in order to improve the estimator performances. Technical support from the laboratory engineer and the motion capture system were crucial for the success of the algorithm. In the end, we obtained a functional implementation of the estimator that was validated on the real robotic platform.</p>